

Charmed: Can Jewellery Tell Us What We Want From Wearable Technology?

Hazel White School of Design, University Of Dundee, DD1 4HT, UK
+ 44 (0)1382 388288, h.white@dundee.ac.uk

Abstract

With the development of smaller and more portable technology, both clothing and jewellery offer potential solutions to the problem of 'wearability'. Jewellery objects often signify emotional attachments, personal stories and have personal meaning to the wearer. Rather than simply being a carrier of technology, could the resonances that jewellery objects gather offer suggestions as to what we might want wearable technology to do? The paper discusses a UK Arts and Humanities Research Council funded project which uses 'charms' to explore what wearers might desire from technologically enabled jewellery. The paper discusses how the research was conducted; the insights gained and suggests future design possibilities.

Conference theme: Usage and Interaction

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Introduction

Design for wearable computing has traditionally fallen within the domain of human-computer interaction (HCI). However new perspectives and methods from other domains have the potential to suggest new and unexpected ways of using wearable technology (Pirhonen and Murphy, 2008). Jewellery is designed to be worn and has personal significance and therefore has potential to inform the design of interactive wearables. (McCarthy, Wright, Wallace and Dearden, 2005). If jewellery had interactive capabilities, what would we want it to do? This paper discusses a UK Arts and Humanities Research Council funded project which explores what wearers might desire from technologically enabled jewellery. The project used 'charms', a jewellery object particularly associated with talismanic qualities and personal significance, as a prop to help gather observations, thoughts and dreams of how technology could affect our lives in a personally and emotionally significant way. The paper discusses how the research was conducted; the insights gained and suggests future design possibilities.

Context

As technology advances, digital devices are increasingly being integrated into everyday life, from *iPhones* to sports monitoring equipment (Nike, 2008). Often this research is technology-led: desktop computers miniaturised into hand-held devices which are retrofitted onto the body using clumsy arm straps or Bluetooth headsets and flash drives 'blinged' up, as if the application of sparkly crystals immediately renders an object wearable and desirable. The translation of analogue artifacts to a digital form can destroy any chance of emotional attachment by focusing on function and missing the personal and contemplative nature of jewellery and personal artifacts. The wooden prayer beads illustrated below have an aesthetic quality, tactility and affordance which the digital prayer counter simply does not (figure1). Jewellery can be commissioned: bespoke items made to the individual requirements. Technology can also be designed for specialization with limited and specific technical functions (Dourish, 2006). This research project explores what wearers might want from *specialized* jewellery.

figure 1 analogue and digital prayer counters

Approach

The study employed a mix of methods from craft, design and social sciences under the umbrella of a people-focused methodology. Methods used included designing and developing jewellery as a key elements of cultural probes (Gaver et. al, 1999) followed by interviews and analysis. Participants designed their own jewellery probe by selecting charms from a wide range of contemporary, traditional and vintage charms and choosing the mode of wearing.

Participants' were all given several charms of the same type eg. locket, figure, abstract, heart to give a level of like for like comparison, with the choice of up to a further ten charms to be selected on aesthetic appeal. They had free choice as to the mode of wearing, selecting from traditional or contemporary silver bracelets, rubber bangles, pins, tie pins, silver neckchains, rubber necklets and keyrings and could customize fastenings choosing from traditional fittings to magnetic catches. (figure 2).

Figure 2: Charms with bracelet

The jewellery was assembled and returned to the participants. Their designs were assembled and returned as part of a probe pack (figure 3) including notebooks, stickers with images of the selected charms, a camera and jewellers pliers to add and remove charms.

figure 3: probe pack

The jewellery was worn over a period of 4-5 weeks, with participants keeping visual and written records how they might like to have individual charms ‘enabled’. At a videoed follow-up interview, participants described their thoughts using their notes and jewellery as prompts. The notebooks and video were then analysed using template analysis (King, 2007) and the POINT analysis framework (Burns and Bontoft, 2006). This paper does not discuss cultural probes as a method, but it is important to emphasise that well designed cultural probes are a creative and engaging method of gaining insights into needs, wants and desires - but they do not produce quantitative results, and were not used to try to produce quantitative data (Boehner et. al 2007). Eight participants took part in the project representing an eclectic mix of jewellery wearers/non-wearers and techno-phobes/technology adopters: the obsessive to the disinterested. The final mix included six women and two men ranging from early twenties to early sixties recruited by publicising the research through professional and social networks. Their occupations ranged from retail assistant, social worker, local government officer, doctoral researcher to retired administrator, gallery assistant and academic. At an initial meeting participants were asked to chart their use of technology and despite trying to recruit some participants with little interest in technology, all participants used technological devices on a regular basis, with those at the low end using mobile phones and the internet on a regular basis to keep in touch with friends and family and those at the opposite end frequently using SMS, digital cameras and the internet.

Jeweller as researcher

A key feature of the research was to harness the insights and capabilities of the jewellery designer: the dialogue between the maker and wearer (a feature of commission-based jewellery design) uses implicit knowledge of materials, modalities of wearing and aesthetics which can uncover the multiple levels on which jewellery is experienced: from a cultural, social and personal resonance to the narrative carried by the object and the physical interaction with the jewellery (Wallace and Dearden, 2005). The knowledge and understanding of materials, manufacturing methods and modes of wearing jewellery also allows the jewellery designer to quickly adapt and manufacture bespoke jewellery to a high standard. Charms were sourced in a number of ways: a number were commissioned specifically for the project, some were purchased from jewellery designers, some from commercial jewellery suppliers and vintage charms were bought at online auction (figure 4). Participants were also encouraged to add items which they already owned, and were provided with links and pliers to attach their own items.

figure 4: selection of commissioned, contemporary, commercial and vintage charms

Commercially available fittings (chains, fastenings, pins and clips) were sourced to produce jewellery which was easily wearable and appropriate to the participants eg. necklace, tie-pin, cuff-links, brooches etc. It is common at this stage of design research to use a lash-up or early prototype, manufactured using different processes and materials from the final object. The jewellery designer as researcher can rapidly manufacture and adapt jewellery pieces to ‘finished’ quality making adoption and use by the participants more likely.

Analysis and Discussion

All the participants wore their jewellery regularly and engaged with the project by making entries and observations in their notebooks and attending follow-up interviews. In the interviews, participants described a wide range of ‘powers’ which they would like to assign to the charms. These were categorised using template analysis and the POINT Analysis Framework (ibid). A wealth of design opportunities were suggested, ranging from the pragmatically functional and currently manufacturable: MP3 players, car and house keys, password keys to the more esoteric, dependant on yet undeveloped technology: from ‘bullshit’ detectors to dream storage and projection devices. In terms of existing physical characteristics some charms were equivalent to the real world counterpart eg. figure representing a specific person or scissors representing a cutting tool and a number of the suggested functions were analogue functions: a calming tool, medicine dispenser, focusing tool (to aid concentration) and an object ‘to make a wish upon’. When digital or ‘special powers’ were considered the charms began to fall into broad categories: *Existing Technical Equivalents*: including information storage and retrieval, communication, alarms and reminders were mentioned, but in many cases these were a very limited function, specific to the wearer and situation eg. A locket that could videophone between two individuals rather than having the multi-functionality of say, an iPhone.

Communication functions: again centered entirely on one to one communication: sending a ‘glow’ to a loved one (like the IDEO Kiss Communicator). Interaction was described as ‘not like a mobile phone’. Communication was broken down into a literal and spiritual sense and could be both positive and negative - one participant described administering punishment electric shocks. Hidden functionality was desirable: with only the owner knowing that the jewellery had ‘special powers’. One person described a charm as enabling her to swear at someone secretly and silently.

Spirituality, Reassurance and Beliefs: many participants treated charms as contemplative objects which was described in terms of spirituality, imagination, creativity and memory. The enabled charms were described variously as a spiritual guide which ‘would help make sense of the world’ and ‘make you believe you are in control’, and a guardian angel. When a moonstone was attributed with the ability to show who was at the door, it was described as ‘looking into a crystal ball’ as opposed to viewing the more prosaic entry phone screen.

Storytelling: charms were used as ‘talking sticks’ to facilitate discussion.

Dreams could be recorded, edited and projected. One participant used a combination of charms to tell a story: with a tape measure representing time, a figure representing a particular individual and a heart to representing love.

Memory: charms could be used to evoke childhood memories – a

miniature opening book suggested a father's cigarette case, recalling a particular incident which allowed the individual to reflect on past and present family relationships. A tape measure charm charted the growth of a young nephew on the other side of the world.

Legacy: a footprint charm could hold lessons and advice from forebears - this was to be controlled by the wearer, as he didn't want to be told constantly how to live his life. A footprint charm was described as 'leaving prints on life'.

Healthcare: suggested functions included diet and fitness aids, with the caveat that they worked as a 'gentle reminder' or 'advisor' rather than a statistical record. The moonstone featured regularly as a sensor of mood, a panic button, and an aid to understand complex data.

Transitional Objects: figure and heart charms tended to be used to signify an emotional connection and were often used as a transitional object for a partner, child or relative from whom the participant was geographically separated. The interactivity desired was often unique and shared between only the participant and one other person for example sending a vibration to partner's corresponding charm to indicate that the wearer is getting (geographically) closer. One participant described in her notes and interview how the figure charm signified a terminally ill friend. The strength of the emotion invested in the charm was demonstrated by the participant contacting the researchers to check the progress of the research and the likely return date of the charm to her (the participants were allowed to select jewellery to keep at the end of the research as thanks for participating). The friend had died in the intervening time, and the charm had taken on the emotional significance and function of a transitional object. In this case any digital function was irrelevant, its significance and meaning changed over time and it could be suggested that its emotional significance may change over time from a transitional object to a carrier of memory.

The element of choice of both charms and mode of wearing was considered to be critical to the likely adoption by the wearer – i.e. allowing the participants in effect to 'design' their jewellery would increase the likelihood of them both wearing and making an emotional connection with the object, and this was borne out during the project. This was very clearly demonstrated by a number of participants arriving for follow-up interview wearing their charms, and being disappointed at having to return them for a period whilst analysis was undertaken. Physical attachment and tactile interaction with jewellery was apparent: participants often held, rubbed or ran chains through hands when discussing charms. The most popular charms to be discussed and attributed interactive capabilities were those designed and made specifically for the project by contemporary jewellers and those sourced from contemporary jewellery designers. High Street and vintage charms proved markedly less attractive, with participants dismissing them as being less personal and engaging. Few participants added items they already owned, so there was not an opportunity to compare whether items in the wearers possession for a longer period generated different outcomes. This could form the basis of a separate study.

Synthesis

This project demonstrates the rich information that can be elicited from a relatively small scoping study using the methods described. The findings are being synthesised in distinct directions: *Smile*, is a research project using jewellery design as part of an augmentative and alternative communication (AAC) system to facilitate communication for people with complex communication needs. Similar methods will be employed to allow people and their carers to identify needs and requirements beyond those of simple functionality, to include personal resonance, meaning and emotion. *Flock*, is a series of interactive jewellery with specialised interactions in which the wearer uses the jewellery as a key to unlock interactive content. again

Conclusions

The research demonstrates that the heuristic approach of the craftsperson, using materials and adapting jewellery in response to the preferred modes of wearing, aesthetic sensibilities and values of the wearer can create wearable artifacts that have a high level of adoption and quickly take on personal meaning and resonance. This has value in a number of design scenarios, including healthcare where technology allows devices to become small enough to wear, e.g. wearable monitoring devices. It is crucial that people develop an emotional attachment to life enhancing technology, rather than viewing it as an encumbrance. The knowledge gained through dialogue between the maker and wearer uncovers the multiple levels on which the jewellery was experienced: from an emotional, cultural, social and personal resonance to the narrative carried by the object and the physical interaction with the jewellery. A wide range of requirements and needs were also signposted for modes of wearing, aesthetics, materials and function. The results suggest that jewellery as a mode of 'carrying' digital capability offers functionality beyond simply mobile communication and hand-held computing. The highly personal and esoteric needs expressed by participants echo Dunne's (2005) desire for the poetic in digital objects. The personal, emotional and expressive language of jewellery is a useful tool for eliciting dreams and desires in a spontaneous and unrestricted way. Jewellery can tell us a great deal about what we might want from might want from wearable technology: and it isn't limited to blinged up USB keys.

References

- Boehner, K., Vertesi, J., Sengers, P., and Dourish, P. (2007). How HCI Interprets the Probes. Proceedings of CHI 2007.
- Bontoft, M and Burns, C (2006). 'The Point Framework: Analysis of User Centered Research'. In conversation and email conversation with H. White 6.2.06.
- Dourish, P (2004), Where the Action is, The Foundations of Embodied Interaction, MIT Press, Mass.
- Dunne, A (2005). 'Hertzian Tales', MIT Press, Cambridge, Mass.
- Gaver, B., Dunne T., Pacenti, E. (1999). Cultural Probes in: interactions, Vol 6, Issue 1, Jan/Feb 1999. ACM Press, NY.
- King, N. (1998) 'Template analysis', in G.Symon and C.Cassell (eds.) Qualitative Methods and Analysis in Organizational Research. London: Sage.
- Nike Sport Band <http://nikeplus.nike.com/nikeplus> accessed 14.5.08.
- Pirhonen, A. and Murphy, M.. Designing for the unexpected: the role of creative group work for emerging interaction design paradigms. Visual Communication (2008) vol. 7 (3).
- Active Crystals Philips-Swarowski <http://www.active-crystals.com/> accessed 14.5.08
- Wallace J, Dearden, A (2005). "Digital Jewellery as Experience." in, Pirhonen, A. Isomaki, H., Roast, C. & Saariluoma, P. (Eds.) Future Interaction Design. Springer-Verlag, London.